

CONSENTIS - An Innovative Framework for Identity and Consent Management for EU Digital and Data Strategies

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Abstract—For many years now, the management of personal information and consent for access and usage remain among the top priorities and challenges in the online world. Individuals demand better control, transparency, and security over their personal data and companies need clear processes compliant with laws and regulations like GDPR, eIDAS, NIS2 etc. This paper presents CONSENTIS, a solution which offers Self-Sovereign Identity and user-centric consent management solutions aiming at empowering users with full control over their data, enabling informed consent, selective data sharing, and real-time transparency. Designed to be agnostic to existing systems, CONSENTIS ensures legal compliance and security through a continuous assessment mechanism, facilitating trust and compliance with EU regulations and strategic digital data initiatives.

Index Terms—Self-sovereign Identity, Consent Management, privacy

I. INTRODUCTION

Digitalization plays a pivotal role in shaping the future of Europe. In this effort, digital data (especially personal data) have become a valuable asset that, when used responsibly and in alignment with fundamental rights, hold the potential for significant benefits.

However, accessing and sharing personal data inside EU is still facing significant problems and affects multiple sectors and activities like research (e.g., in healthcare sector), business development (e.g., AI and big data analysis), safety and security (e.g., Cyber Threat Intelligence) etc. These challenges stem from the lack of solutions (across multiple levels i.e., technical, operational, legal etc.) that can facilitate the sharing and process of personal information, and at the same time

protect the rights that are conferred upon the individuals by relevant legal frameworks like the eIDAS Regulation, GDPR, and NIS2 Directive.

At the same time, end-users continue to struggle with the management of their personal data and online identities. The endless creation of new accounts, the “shady practices” often used by service providers, their limited expertise and/or fatigue etc., lead to inability or even complete loss of control over personal information. New approaches for self-sovereign identities (SSIs) are moving towards the correct direction providing more transparent solutions for consent and management, yet many issues related to usability, user experience, lack of technical skills etc. still need to be resolved [1], [2].

In the era of big data analysis and data spaces, CONSENTIS examines the issue of identity and consent management inside a wider ecosystem of actors and services, instead of a process between two end points (e.g., a user and a service provider). Our main goal is to break the barriers (technological, administrative, legal etc.) between users and other stakeholders (service providers, third parties, research community etc.) and through a set of solutions facilitate data usage in way that a) guarantees that users are always in full control of their data and b) stakeholders have the ability to locate, request and access and use personal data in a transparent and lawful way.

To this end, CONSENTIS introduces an innovative SSI and user-centric consent management framework designed to: (a) Empower users with full control over their digital identities and personal data usage; (b) Provide transparent, secure, and privacy-enhancing mechanisms for consent management; (c)

Be agnostic to existing services, technologies, and formats, ensuring broad interoperability; and (d) Maintain compliance with key EU regulations and legal frameworks through continuous risk and security assessment.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section II reviews the current State of the Art in Identity and Consent Management. Section III presents the conceptual architecture of the CONSENTIS framework, which empowers users to maintain control over their identity information and monitor data sharing through a solution-agnostic approach, ensuring compatibility with existing services and technologies. Section IV demonstrates two representative use cases, focusing on electronic health data. Finally, Section V presents the conclusions and outlines future directions for further development.

II. STATE OF THE ART

This section reviews the latest advancements in methods, and regulations related to secure personal data management, dynamic consent systems, identity management, and privacy-enhancing solutions.

A. Dynamic Consent Management

Several initiatives have introduced Consent Management approaches aiming at empowering users to maintain control over their data [3], [4]. Notably, a flexible and dynamic approach, as outlined in [5], has been developed to capture consent and preserve digital evidence for legal purposes. The solution described in [6], focuses on maximizing the quality, replicability, and relevance of decisional autonomy in researcher-participant communication. The EnCoRe project [7] stands out for its development of reliable and enforceable privacy-enabled dynamic consent capabilities. Additionally, in the work of [8], a high-level modeling language for distributed service oriented systems has been introduced, offering a GDPR-based formal design framework for consent management. Still, the above methods have limitations: (a) they are centralized solutions, which raise concerns about the lack of trusted proof of data provenance, accountability, transparency, security, and privacy ([3], [5], [7], [8]); (b) they provide very limited rights to users ([6]); and (c) they may allow unauthorized manipulation or misuse of granted consents and data without users' knowledge ([3], [6], [8]). In addition to the above, several Blockchain-enabled consent management schemes have been proposed [9], [10], particularly in the eHealth domain. These schemes use smart contracts to represent individual consent and enable requesters to access health data. Although not suffering from the limitations above, [4], [9] and [10] focus solely on healthcare.

B. Identity Management and Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI)

Identity management has been an intensively researched topic. On Web standards and specifications, W3C released the specifications for a) Decentralized identifiers (DIDs) [11], a new type of identifier that enables verifiable, decentralized digital identity and b) Verifiable Credentials (VCs) Data Model [12], which are the electronic equivalent of existing physical credentials. The Identifiers and Discovery Working

Group (DIF) is working for the development of protocols and systems that enable creation, resolution, and discovery of decentralized identifiers across underlying decentralized systems, like blockchains and distributed ledgers. In industry, several companies extend these specifications and use blockchain to build their own Identity Management (IdM) systems, such as Microsoft with Microsoft Identity and ION network [13], IBM with IBM identity [14], Ping Identity [15] etc. At the same time the eIDAS [16], EU Digital Identity Wallet [17], along with the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [18] are some of the solutions that the public sector is adopting for the management of identities and privacy of personal information. Although high-quality, these systems are centralized and tailored to specific contexts (e.g., company, public sector). Other publications also introduce systems that use blockchains as the underlying technology to store users' identities, or their representations. Such solutions include Blockstack [19], BPDIMS [20], LifeID [21] etc. These efforts introduce various blockchain-based solutions for self-sovereign identity but still do not address the critical issues of consent management and user experience. Finally, DNS-IdM [22] enables identity discovery using both permissioned and permissionless blockchains but offers little for identity or consent management.

C. Privacy Enhancing Technologies for data sharing

Recently, research has focused on techniques to ensure privacy and security in data sharing and collaborative analytics. Differential Privacy (DP) is a key approach, adding noise to protect privacy but reducing data accuracy, highlighting the privacy-accuracy trade-off [23]. To address this, DP can be combined with Homomorphic Encryption (HE), which enables computations on encrypted data but is limited by noise accumulation and high computational costs, making it more suitable for simple, two-party scenarios. While Microsoft's SEAL [24] introduces noise to plaintext values, limiting consecutive operations, it remains applicable to computations with a fixed, small number of arithmetic operations. When using HE with data from multiple parties, a significant challenge arises concerning the ownership of the single secret key. To address this issue, a multi-party HE scheme based on the BFV scheme [25] implemented in the SEAL library was proposed in [26]. Conventional encryption mechanisms are more robust than DP and HE without preserving data utility for subsequent analysis. RSA encryption [27] remains a state-of-the-art and robust cryptographic technique, serving as the default choice in numerous applications due to its proven strength and reliability.

D. Regulatory and Legal aspects for personal data

Since 2020, the European Commission has introduced a series of legislative proposals in line with its digital and data strategies, namely the Digital Services Act (DSA), the Digital Markets Act (DMA), the Data Governance Act (DGA) etc. Also, towards fostering an innovative data economy, the

European Strategy for data (Data Strategy) identifies nine common European Data Spaces (Health, Industrial, Agriculture, Finance, Mobility, Green Deal, Energy, Public Administration, and Skills). At the same time, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (General Data Protection Regulation, GDPR), the Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2018/1725 for Union institutions, bodies, offices and agencies, and eIDAS (Electronic Identification, Authentication and Trust Services) for secure and seamless electronic transactions across EU borders, state that data processors have to cater for managing and enforcing the right of data subjects to control what data about them is exposed and how it is used, covering different aspects, including transparency (Art. 15: Right of Access), unlinkability (data minimization principle) and intervenability (right to erasure, right to rectification, right to turn to data protection authorities). In this context, data processors must update their privacy consent management mechanisms and reassess personal data processing operations to monitor all data sources and processing tasks.

E. Blockchain Technology for personal data management

Blockchain technology has witnessed significant advancements in recent years, supporting applications in various sectors such as finance, healthcare, IoT, and cybersecurity [28]. It's important to note that in certain blockchain structures, smart contracts (SCs) are executed by integrating external data to trigger scheduled orders or events. To achieve this, cryptographic techniques like Zero-Knowledge (ZK) proof systems come into play, enabling the implementation of desired functionalities without exposing the external data initiating a transaction. Ethereum [29], an open-source blockchain platform, is well-known for introducing these SCs. Concerning personal data protection, there are several concerns about blockchain's compliance with data protection laws such as GDPR [30], especially in specific contexts (e.g., public permissionless blockchains). Determining the data controller(s) or data processor(s) can be challenging in some cases. Using blockchain for personal data processing raises various data protection and privacy concerns, particularly in terms of adhering to the data minimization principle and ensuring the rights of data subjects.

Beyond State of the Art:

Considering the above context, CONSENTIS aims to enhance the security of personal data compatible with EU data regulations through a variety of options. Combining the utilization of blockchain technology, smart contracts and advanced privacy-preserving techniques, CONSENTIS is designed to offer solutions to address data protection through a dynamic and transparent consent management system which ensures privacy, accountability and compliance. Focusing on user control over their personal information, CONSENTIS introduces SSI mechanisms that enable lawful and transparent identity operations, which, alongside advanced PPTs like homomorphic encryption and differential privacy, provide confidentiality on such a complex process. By applying these solutions in a transparent manner, CONSENTIS provides a robust, secure,

and user-centric approach to managing personal data in an EU compliant and privacy-focused manner.

III. SOLUTION ARCHITECTURE

A high-level architectural view of the CONSENTIS framework is provided in Fig. 1. For clarity reasons all internal components are grouped in three main categories: those that exist in the Data Subject (user) side, those in the Data holder, processor (service provider, third party etc.) side, and the rest that exist in the Trust and Security plane and provide the security and trust features of the system.

Fig. 1. CONSENTIS Conceptual Architecture

DATA SUBJECT:

A. CONSENTIS Identity Wallet

The CONSENTIS Identity Wallet is a modular mobile application designed to help users collect, store and manage their digital identities, credentials, consent policies etc. Through a user-friendly interface (UI), users can organize their identities, receive notifications, monitor the usage of data and define policies. Integration with other identity wallet implementations (e.g. EUDI) is supported (in fact CONSENTIS wallet can be viewed as an extension of EUDI with additional features), along with the existing features for SSI operations based on DIDs and VCs.

B. Data Interception - Listener

To prevent mobile applications from accessing, collecting, storing and transmitting information without the users' approval, the Data Interception-Listener module is responsible for enhancing user privacy. It analyzes data processing activities, including cookies and third-party interactions on the user's device. Upon detecting new data transmissions, the Consent Policy Manager will verify compliance with existing policies or trigger policy updates. While this module assumes that applications act honestly and submit all collected information, the Data Inspection and Audit module below is able to identify malicious actors.

C. Data Inspection and Audit module

This component enables users and regulatory bodies to assess mobile applications' data practices against user preferences and regulatory requirements through an interface. This automated process involves four steps: 1. Network Traffic Decryption (e.g. by utilizing tools like the PiRogue Tool Suite); 2. Data Type Identification, detecting the type and nature of the collected and transmitted data; 3. Data Usage Analysis, monitoring how data is processed and transmitted to third-party servers; and 4. Comparison with User Preferences, flagging discrepancies between collected data and user-defined policies.

TRUST AND SECURITY PLANE:

D. CONSENTIS Consent policy manager

This module securely records and stores user identities, metadata and consent transactions with third-party services, enabling users to maintain control over their data and make informed decisions. The fundamental elements of the consent include the data subject, specific personal data, the identity of the entity requesting consent, evidence of the agreement, a description of the context (purposes, time, operations, territory etc.) and the status of consent (valid or invalid). The component generates consent policies embedded in contracts, handles consent-related requests, records transactions on a blockchain for tamper-proof traceability, and enables users to modify or revoke consent as needed.

E. CONSENTIS Smart Contract generator

The Smart Contract generator leverages Smart Contracts on blockchains to provide users with full control over their consent throughout the entire data lifecycle. By combining predefined contract templates with the consent policies and contracts produced by the Consent Policy Manager, it efficiently enforces fine-grained access controls to data streams while ensuring compliance with privacy and security regulations. This component consists of two core modules: 1. The Generator, which produces machine-readable contracts following FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles; and 2. The Finder, which identifies datasets and smart contracts relevant to specific data processing operations.

F. CONSENTIS Discovery Mechanism

This module enhances privacy and security by providing service providers looking for identity-related information of a specific subject with the location of the data and at the same time informing the user to accept or reject this request. It is based on the work presented in [31] and uses a network of nodes (similar to Identity Hubs [32]) that don't store any actual user identities. This mechanism relies on a modified W3C Verifiable Credential model that indicates the data location and supported operations (e.g., authentication, age validation), without containing any actual data and does not introduce any kind of new global identifiers, making the CONSENTIS Discovery mechanism agnostic to existing protocols and services.

G. Distributed Ledger Technologies for secure storage and sharing

The CONSENTIS framework leverages Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLT) to establish a decentralized infrastructure that ensures the integrity and authenticity of the stored data and the actions that occur to them. To address challenges imposed by regulations like the GDPR, this module can assess privacy-enhancing techniques (e.g. private permissioned blockchains), and purely cryptographic solutions (e.g., zero-knowledge proofs and ring confidential transactions) for integration.

DATA HOLDER, PROCESSOR:

H. Privacy Enhancing Technologies for Secure Data Sharing

This module enables the secure and privacy-preserving data sharing among stakeholders, (data subjects, service providers, data processors etc.). By leveraging blockchain technology, it ensures tamper-proof record-keeping through a decentralized ledger. Moreover, the module integrates privacy-enhancing technologies (PETs) to strengthen data confidentiality and conformance to privacy regulations like GDPR. Non-numerical data types can be protected using traditional cryptography (RSA, hash functions etc.).

I. Privacy and Data Usage Control

The Privacy and Usage Control module enforces machine-processable privacy and data usage policies based on user preferences and Smart Contracts, extending the Data Privacy Vocabulary [33]. It ensures that data are shared and processed only under predefined conditions, including complex consent rules.

The module enables dynamic dataset discovery by matching Smart Contracts with available resources, updating privacy policies using knowledge representation and reasoning methods. It also integrates PETs and knowledge graphs to formalize policies, leveraging ontologies like UsablePrivacy [34] and GDPRtEXT [35]. This approach ensures transparent, policy-driven access control, allowing users to monitor who accesses their data and under what conditions.

J. Risk & Impact Assessor module

The Risk & Impact Assessor module evaluates the risks associated with data processing and sharing operations, leveraging a Mitigate Risk Assessment solution. It will analyze security threats, vulnerabilities, risk mitigation measures (e.g., encryption), and data protection requirements to determine potential business and technical impacts.

Based on its assessment, the module generates a risk mitigation strategy, recommending security controls and adjustments to enhance data integrity, availability, and confidentiality.

K. Legal and Deviations Assessment

Finally the Legal and Deviations Assessment module evaluates data usage and privacy policies against Smart Contracts published on the blockchain to ensure compliance with legal

and regulatory standards such as GDPR, the Data Governance Act and the Data Act.

It also assesses compliance with ethical frameworks like ALTAI [36], ensuring human oversight in data sharing. By automating consent management, it aims to facilitate scalable and trustworthy data sharing in the EU single market, validating the legal integrity of Smart Contracts.

L. Conclusion

CONSENTIS is a complicated system with multiple components to orchestrate, and the need to follow EU standards on SSI and data spaces. An agile development process with multiple iterations of testing and refinement is expected to address the integration challenges.

IV. USE CASES

This section explains how CONSENTIS supports identity and consent management in two healthcare use cases involving multiple actors and personal data interactions.

A. Electronic health data exchange between an insurance company and a public healthcare system

For this use case, a user wants to buy a new life insurance from an insurance company. To complete the process, the insurance company needs specific health information. At the same time the user wants to keep his full medical history private and have full control over what is shared.

With CONSENTIS solutions (Fig. 2), the insurance company will initially request from the Discovery Mechanism a location of health data for this user. The user is notified through the CONSENTIS Identity Wallet to either approve or reject this request and can also select which provider (e.g. hospital or central healthcare system) can provide the requested information. The Discovery Mechanism returns to the insurance company a Temporary ID (that corresponds to the user’s account) and the location (Hospital URL) to contact. Then the insurance company requests (using the Temporary ID) from the hospital the health data it needs. The hospital checks the consent policy for this information through the Consent Policy Manager and the DLT module and notifies the user to update it or reject the request. Then the user updates consent ONLY for the data he/she allows to be shared and the Smart Contract Generator enforces the fine-grained consent agreement via Smart Contracts on the DLT module. The rest of the CONSENTIS modules complement the process, running in the background and ensuring privacy and security.

For this scenario the following should be clarified: (a) The entity that hosts the user health data is actually the National Healthcare Registry, however for the purposes of generalizing the use case we present the Hospital as the Service Provider of Healthcare services; (b) The Temporary ID is used only once. After that it is updated and a third party (insurance company) cannot ask again for new information about this user, unless it requests a new Temporary ID from the Discovery mechanism which in turn will notify the user.

Fig. 2. Electronic health data exchange between an insurance company and a public healthcare system

B. Use of electronic health data in the context of EU Data Spaces

This use case focuses on EU Data Spaces and describes a data transfer between data intermediaries/brokers etc. and third parties that need this information for business development, analytics, research, AI training etc.

In this case (Fig. 3), the insurance company needs from the National Healthcare Registry data about all users that meet specific criteria (e.g., above a certain age, with specific health issues) to conduct e.g., a cost analysis for its offered services. The National Healthcare Registry, upon receiving this request, checks which users meet the criteria and cross-checks (on the DLT module’s blockchain) their consent policies for sharing their information. For users that have not already consented, a notification is sent via the CONSENTIS Identity Wallet about whether they want to update their policy through the Consent Policy Manager and the Smart Contract Generator. For those who agree, their data are included in the response request. For those who refuse, the HIS (Hospital Information System) agnostic CONSENTIS component processes their data with a set of privacy-enhancing technologies through the PET module and produces an extra dataset, compliant to existing regulations.

Fig. 3. Use of electronic health data in the context of EU Data Spaces

For this scenario the following need to be clarified: (a) Users would perhaps voluntarily share their data for the common

good (e.g., for research purposes) or ask for something in return (e.g., in the case of a business service). This is a valid practice that takes place in many cases, however it is outside the scope of CONSENTIS which will only focus on the technical aspects of this scenario; (b) With CONSENTIS, we aim to create higher-quality datasets enriched with user-approved information through informed consent — a feature missing from existing methods.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented the overall vision & main concepts behind CONSENTIS, aiming to design, deliver & validate a framework that will allow users to efficiently manage their identities, protect their privacy and provide informed consent for personal data operations that take place across different contexts and administrative domains. Particular emphasis is given to alignment with EU regulations for data privacy as well as the EU landscape, supporting cross-border, cross-organisational, and cross-function collaboration and coordination, tailored to the needs of users, data holders, service providers, and relevant EU entities and bodies.

In terms of next steps, the individual components comprising CONSENTIS will be developed and integrated. Moreover, a complete validation process will take place in the project and results are expected to be published after one year. Further, the resulting integrated framework will be validated in the context of 2 use cases operating on healthcare data. This will allow for a holistic assessment of CONSENTIS and its vision, collecting concrete evidence of its applicability, along with valuable feedback and pointers for its further refinement.

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